

Lipid/ZIF-8 biocomposites based on liposomes or vesicles: *in-situ* formation, and preliminary evaluation as delivery vehicles for hydrophobic drugs

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Integrating lipid self-assemblies with metal-organic frameworks (MOFs) creates biocomposites ideal for encapsulation, protection, and delivery of functional species. This can be achieved using preformed MOFs or through *in situ* MOF formation. Herein, we report the *in-situ* formation of ZIF-8 MOF particles in the presence of two lipid self-assemblies (vesicles or liposomes), generating two types of hybrid lipid/ZIF-8 biocomposites. Each lipid assembly can be used to encapsulate hydrophobic actives into the hybrid lipid/ZIF-8 biocomposites, demonstrated with Nile Red and Astaxanthin (ATX) as representative cargo. *In vitro* digestion of ATX-loaded hybrid lipid/ZIF-8 particles in simulated intestinal fluid (SIF) shows distinct release kinetics: liposome-based particles offer a more sustained release compared to vesicle-based biocomposites. Intriguingly, in various media (water, simulated gastric fluid, bicarbonate, and SIF), the sodalite ZIF-8 topology in liposome-based lipid/ZIF-8 particles undergoes a crystalline phase transition to the denser, more-stable phase ZIF-C. This phase transition, along with a deeper internalization of ATX in liposome-based particles, accounts for the differences in release kinetics. In summary, our study provides valuable insights for the synthesis of hybrid lipid/ZIF-8 biocomposites, the encapsulation of hydrophobic molecules, the importance of investigating potential crystalline phase transitions of MOFs in different media, and their potential as drug delivery vehicles.

1. Introduction

When surfactants, amphiphilic block polymers, or lipids are dispersed in aqueous solutions at a certain concentration, they tend to self-assemble into a variety of supramolecular structures. The shapes and sizes of these structures are determined by their concentration and packing parameters, such as the volume of the hydrophobic chain, the optimum head-group area and the length of the hydrophobic chain.^[1] For example, at critical micelle concentration, surfactants and amphiphilic block copolymers form micelles that can be spherical, prolate or oblate.^[2] On the other hand, in dilute solutions, amphiphilic lipids self-assemble into small bubble-like structures called *vesicles* (derived from the Latin term *vesicula*).^[3] Vesicles can be formed by

bilayer membranes, which can organize into unilamellar or multilamellar (onion-like) structures. Vesicles created from a bilayer membrane comprising phospholipids and cholesterol lipids are named as liposomes.^[4] The unique shape and size, structural flexibility and dynamics of vesicles play a crucial role in their remarkable functionality, making them the most extensively investigated nanocarriers for therapeutically active compounds in the field of medicine. Due to the amphiphilic nature of lipids and their organization within closed structures, lipid self-assemblies can encapsulate different types of cargo in their different compartments: hydrophobic molecules, within their membrane; hydrophilic compounds, within their aqueous internal cavity; and amphiphilic substances, throughout their structure.^[5] Importantly, lipids such as fatty acids, sterols, glycerolipids and glycerophospholipids are the primary structural components of cell membranes, playing a key role in various biological processes, including cell metabolism, and signaling.^[6] This biocompatibility is crucial for their use as carriers for therapeutics.^[7]

Despite the interest in vesicles and liposomes as drug delivery vehicles, they suffer from serious drawbacks, including uptake and rapid degradation by specialized cells (the reticuloendothelial system), and an inability to release their cargo in a sustained manner over an extended period. To overcome these difficulties, liposomes have been combined with other materials (*e.g.* inorganic nanoparticles and polymers) to create more stable and versatile delivery platforms.^[8] For example, the literature contains several studies on temporary depot delivery systems of polymeric materials for controlling the release of pre-encapsulated, drug-loaded liposomes.^{[9],[10]}

Metal-organic frameworks (MOFs) are highly porous crystalline hybrid materials known for their applications in gas storage, catalysis, sensors, and separation. Recently, combinations of MOFs with several (bio)molecules such as neurotransmitters, small molecules, nucleic acids, proteins, vesicles, liposomes, viruses, and even whole cells have been increasingly explored for drug delivery.^{[11]-[14]} These include lipid-on-MOF systems, which are MOFs whose outer crystal structure is functionalized with lipids, and which have shown superior colloidal stability and biocompatibility in biological fluids relative to their constituent MOF component alone, through longer blood-circulation times, better cellular internalization and greater dispersion. For example, Wang *et al.* demonstrated the functionalization of Zr-based MOF particles with 1,2-dioleoyl-sn-glycero-3-phosphate (DOPA; a phosphate-based lipid), resulting in a stable colloidal suspension of hydrophilic MOFs in low-polarity media.^[15] Similarly, phenolic lipids have been effectively used to functionalize MOF particles.^[16] Other studies have explored the effective storage of dye molecules in lipid-coated MOFs, preventing premature release in

cancer cells;^[17] and the development of lipid surface-modified, drug-loaded MOF particles with high drug-loading capacity, biodegradability and biocompatibility.^[18] There have also been studies on MOF particles encapsulating lipid assemblies for drug delivery systems. For example, Herbert *et al.* reported immobilization of metastable lipid and protein-lipid supramolecular complexes within ZIF-8 particles, which protected the cargo against chemical and physical stressors.^[19] Similarly, Kumari *et al.* protected liposomes by encapsulating them in ZIF-8 for mechanical protection, and explored the potential of such a ZIF-8 biocomposite for delivery of genetic material as an alternative to syringe-and-needle-based vaccine administration.^{[20][22]}

Here, we examine how two types of cationic lipid structures, specifically vesicles and liposomes, interact with the well-known Metal-Organic Framework (MOF) called Zeolitic Imidazole Framework-8 (ZIF-8) during its formation. Note that, while both lipid structures selected are lipid bilayer vesicles, we herein have differentiated them as vesicles (formed by the lipids CTAB and cholesterol) and as liposomes (made of the phospholipid DMPC and cholesterol) for clarity. ZIF-8 composed of Zn metal ion and 2-methylimidazole (2-MiM) ligand, is commonly used in creating biocomposites and for drug delivery applications since it offers numerous advantageous properties for drug delivery systems, including minimal toxicity (with a median lethal dose-LD50 of 0.35 for Zn and 1.4 g/kg for 2-methylimidazole);^{[23]-[25]} it can be synthesized in an aqueous medium at ambient temperature, exhibits high porosity (typically exceeding 1200 m²/g); and demonstrates stability under standard neutral conditions while degrading rapidly in acidic environments due to protonation.^{[26]-[28]} We found that in-situ formation of ZIF-8 particles in the presence of either lipid self-assembly generates colloidal biocomposites, hybrid lipid/ZIF-8 particles, in which the lipids are mainly assembled on the outer surface of the ZIF-8 particles (Figure 1a and 1e). These results show that the one-pot encapsulation approach can also lead to the spontaneous, direct formation of lipid-on-MOF systems, without the need of coating pre-synthesized MOF particles. Moreover, in the case of liposomes, the resulting lipid/ZIF-8 biocomposites also internalize some of these lipid assemblies into the ZIF-8 particles (Figure 1e). We also studied the stability of the hybrid lipid/ZIF-8 biocomposites in various physiologically relevant media, observing that, unlike bare ZIF-8 particles, upon contact with bicarbonate and simulated gastric medium (SGM), our lipid/ZIF-8 particles tend to undergo phase transformation (from ZIF-8 to ZIF-C). Finally, we demonstrated that lipid self-assemblies (vesicles and liposomes) can effectively serve as vehicles for encapsulating highly hydrophobic and inherently unstable species within ZIF-8

particles, an objective that remains challenging. Thus, by pre-encapsulating representative hydrophobic molecules (*i.e.* the fluorophore Nile Red (NR) and the antioxidant drug Astaxanthin (3,3'-dihydroxy- β,β' -carotene-4,4'-dione; ATX)) within the lipid membrane of vesicles and liposomes, we successfully generated hybrid lipid /ZIF-8 biocomposites that efficiently encapsulate both hydrophobic molecules. In the lipid/ZIF-8 biocomposites made with vesicles (hereafter called vesicle/ZIF-8 biocomposites), the hydrophobic molecule linked to the lipid membrane is predominantly found on the outer surface of the biocomposite. In contrast, in those made with liposomes (hereafter called liposome/ZIF-8 biocomposites), the hydrophobic molecule/lipid material is distributed both on the surface and within the ZIF-8. Both types of biocomposites encapsulating the drug ATX show promise as delivery vehicles for ATX, offering different release properties. Moreover, our findings highlight that the above-mentioned phase transformations observed in lipid/ZIF-8 biocomposites within biological media could be very important for their potential applications in drug delivery.

2. Results and Discussion

2.1. Synthesis of hybrid lipid/ZIF-8 biocomposites

We began by preparing the cationic vesicles (diameter: ~ 200 nm) and liposomes (diameter: ~ 100 nm) by solvent evaporation and ultrasound homogenization, using a mixture of cholesterol and CTAB for the vesicles (**Figure 1b**), or a mixture of DMPC, cholesterol and positively charged cholesterol (Chol+) for the liposomes (**Figure 1f**; **Figure S1**, Supporting information). We chose these compositions for the optimal stabilization of the products, and the ability of the cationic components to promote nucleation and growth of sub-micrometric ZIF-8 particles.^[29] Thus, lipid/ZIF-8 hybrid particles were synthesized by first adding an aqueous solution of zinc acetate dihydrate containing the aforementioned vesicles or liposomes to an aqueous solution of 2-MiM, which afforded a white flocculate (**Figure 1a** and **1e**). Next, the hybrid particles were left at room temperature for 2 hours, washed, and then freeze-dried for 2 days. For comparison purposes, bare ZIF-8 particles were also synthesized using the aforementioned conditions. This yielded cationic cubic ZIF-8 particles with a mean particle size of 165 ± 2 nm and a measured Brunauer-Emmett-Teller (BET) surface area of 1445 ± 10 m²/g (**Figure S2** and **S3**, Supporting Information). **Table S1** summarizes the characterization data for the hybrid ZIF-8 particles (Supporting Information). For both systems, we obtained cationic (zeta potential: +31 mV to +38 mV) and highly monodisperse colloidal cubic particles in water.

The mean particle size of the vesicle/ZIF-8 particles was 215 ± 3 nm, whereas that of the liposome/ZIF-8 particles was 174 ± 2 nm (Figure 1c and 1g; Figure S2, Supporting Information). Importantly, the size, shape and charge of the hybrid particles did not differ when the vesicles or liposomes were added to the solution of zinc acetate dihydrate *versus* when they were added to the solution of 2-MiM. Additionally, no free liposomes or vesicles were detected by cryo-TEM in the supernatant of the hybrid-particle samples (Figure S4, Supporting Information). PXRD indicated that all the hybrid biocomposites were crystalline sodalite ZIF-8 (Figure 1d and 1h). Nitrogen-sorption measurements on the synthesized biocomposites corroborated their microporosity: the measured BET surface areas for both types of hybrid lipid/ZIF-8 particles (range: ~ 1200 m²/g to 1400 m²/g) are lower than the reported values for ZIF-8 alone, probably because of the partial encapsulation of lipid assemblies within the MOF crystal (Figure S3, Supporting Information).

Figure 1. (a,e) Schematics of the formation and structure of lipid/ZIF-8 hybrid biocomposites: (a) vesicle/ZIF-8 and (e) liposome/ZIF-8. (b,f) Cryo-TEM images of (b) CTAB/Chol vesicles

and (f) DMPC-Chol-Chol(+) liposomes. Scale bar: 200 nm. (c,g) SEM images of particles of the biocomposites (c) vesicle/ZIF-8 and (g) liposome/ZIF-8. Scale bar: 500 nm. (d,h) PXRD spectra of the biocomposites (d) vesicle/ZIF-8 (red) and (h) liposome/ZIF-8 (red), as compared to pure ZIF-8 (black).

To study the interaction of lipid assemblies (vesicles or liposomes) with ZIF-8 precursors, we conducted time-resolved synchrotron small-angle X-ray scattering (SAXS) experiments using a stopped-flow device. The detailed experimental setup and measurement conditions are disclosed in the Supporting Information (Section S3, Supporting Information). The stopped-flow setup is ideal for studying the formation of ZIF-8 over short time periods by monitoring the diffraction of the [110] reflection at $q = 5.3 \text{ nm}^{-1}$.^[30] In our study, we examined the particle formation process of the vesicle/ZIF-8, the liposome/ZIF-8 and the ZIF-8 systems as a reference over time (0.05 s to 20 min). For this purpose, we separately injected two precursor solutions into a capillary: a first precursor solution, which consisted of vesicles or liposomes and zinc acetate; and a second precursor solution, which was composed of 2-MiM and CTAB. The combination of the precursor solutions resulted in the detection of diffraction patterns, depicted in **Figure 2a** and S7 (Supporting Information). Time-resolved analysis of the scattering signals revealed an amorphous phase within the first seconds of precursor mixing (lipid assemblies and ZIF-8 reactants), similarly to the experimental observations by Carraro *et al.*^[30] and Herbert *et al.*^[19] which employed proteins and liposomes as biomimetic mineralization agents during ZIF-8 synthesis. Analysis based on the calculation of invariant and the fitting of the particle form factor^{[30][31]} further indicated that the growth rate (Figure S8-S10 and Tables S3-S5), size ($1.53 \pm 0.73 \text{ nm}$) and morphology of the amorphous particles is similar between vesicle/ZIF-8, liposome/ZIF-8 and pure ZIF-8 (control; for details, see Figure S10 and Table S5, Supporting Information). The scattering patterns of the lipid/ZIF-8 particles showed an absence of the scattering hump characteristic of individual vesicles and liposomes, suggesting the disassembly of lipid vesicles or liposomes in the presence of ZIF-8 precursors; for comparison, see the diffraction patterns of pure liposomes and vesicles in Figure S6 (Supporting Information), which show a broad scattering hump in the low q region. However, in the investigated liposome/ZIF-8 system, the [110] reflection of ZIF-8 at 5.3 nm^{-1} became visible after a few seconds, indicating the formation of crystalline ZIF-8 with sodalite topology (Figure 2a).^[30] The time evolution of the peak area of the [110] reflection was fitted with the Johnson-Mehl-Avrami-Kolmogorov (JMAK) model, which is used to identify characteristic parameters of the

crystallization process (Equation S2, Supporting Information).^[32] For example, we could calculate the induction period of crystallization (t_0), which is the time for producing a nucleus with sufficient size for crystal growth.^[33] According to the Avrami theory,^[34] this time defines a time point when the nucleation begins but is not yet detectable through macroscopic changes (*e.g.* diffraction peaks are absent as the fraction of amorphous materials largely exceeds the crystalline one).^{[35][36]} For the liposome/ZIF-8 system, the induction period was 2 ± 3 s (Figure 2b), indicating the almost instantaneous propensity of the system towards crystallization. By using the same JMKA model, the induction periods of vesicle/ZIF-8 and pure ZIF-8 (control) were 13 ± 5 s and 24 ± 2 s, respectively. This indicates that both vesicle/ZIF-8 and pure ZIF-8 systems require more time to originate the very first crystalline domain. A second parameter that was determined was the growth time τ . The liposome/ZIF-8 system showed the shortest $\tau = 59 \pm 3$ s, followed by the vesicle/ZIF-8 system with 95 ± 2 s, and the ZIF-8 with 197 ± 5 s. Finally, we evaluated the slope n , which was 2.7 ± 0.2 for the liposome/ZIF-8, suggesting a two-dimensional growth of the grain.^[37] In quite contrast, both vesicle/ZIF-8 and ZIF-8 exhibited a slope < 2 , indicative of one-dimensional growth of the grain (1.9 ± 0.1 and 1.9 ± 0.2 respectively, Table S4). To visually highlight the onset of crystallization, the 10% limit of crystallization, typically used to visualize a threshold of crystallization in kinetic processes,^[38] was marked in Figure 2b. Arrows indicate the faster crystallization of the liposome/ZIF-8 particles compared to the vesicle/ZIF-8 and ZIF-8 particles.

Figure 2. a) Time evolution of the SAXS diffraction patterns for the liposome/ZIF-8 systems, in which the amorphous to crystalline transition is shown. Reflections of the [110] and [200] sod ZIF-8 planes are marked with blue arrows. b) Integrated peak area of [110] sod ZIF-8 reflection over time with the fit of the JMAK model.^{[32][34]} The arrows refer to the 10% of the max crystallization intensity to indicate a common crystallization threshold value reached during the different amorphous-to-crystalline processes.

To confirm the incorporation of the lipid assemblies onto and into the lipid/ZIF-8 and study their location within the particles, we next prepared NR fluorescently-labeled vesicles and liposomes, encapsulating NR into their lipidic membranes (~ 0.6 mg/mL NR in the vesicles, and ~ 0.9 mg/mL NR in the liposomes)^{[39]-[41]} (**Figure 3a** and **3e**). The NR@vesicles (mean

particle size: 229 ± 12 nm) and NR@liposomes (mean particle size: 731 ± 55 nm) both exhibited a unilamellar spherical morphology (Figure S11, Supporting Information). Next, the respective lipid/ZIF-8 biocomposites were prepared, using the aforementioned protocol. Like the lipid/ZIF-8 particles, the corresponding lipid/ZIF-8 biocomposites incorporating NR exhibited a cubic morphology, comparable crystallinity and microporosity, and a positive surface charge (Figure 3b and 3f; Table S6; Figure S12 and S13). However, they were larger than their bare homologs, with mean particle sizes of 438 ± 9 nm for NR@vesicle/ZIF-8, and 918 ± 6 nm for NR@liposome/ZIF-8 (Figure S14, Supporting Information).

The first evidence of incorporation of the lipid assemblies was the pink color of the resulting biocomposites, which is characteristic of NR (Figure 3d and 3h, left). Measurements of the NR-incorporation efficiencies yielded values of $66\% \pm 6\%$ for the NR@vesicle/ZIF-8, and $71\% \pm 1\%$ for the NR@liposome/ZIF-8 biocomposites. NR is a lipophobic probe widely used for the staining of lipid membranes. In our biocomposites, NR stains via hydrophobic interaction the lipid membrane in both vesicle and liposomes assemblies, and it was used to indirectly observe the spatial localization and penetration extent of lipids in ZIF-8 particles using confocal microscopy. 3D Imaris reconstruction images of the NR@vesicle/ZIF-8 particles revealed that the lipidic assemblies incorporating NR (in red) are mainly located on the outer surface of and partially cover the ZIF-8 particles (in grey) (Figure 3c, left). Even in the cross-section images (Figure 3c, right), it is evident that the lipids do not penetrate the interior of the ZIF-8, as the grey area of the ZIF-8 remains unchanged in the Z-stack. This observation indicated that, upon formation of ZIF-8, the lipidic assemblies are incorporated onto the resultant ZIF-8 particles through continuous lipidic supramolecular disassembly/reassembly processes. For the NR@liposome/ZIF-8 biocomposites, 3D Imaris reconstruction confocal microscopy images showed that lipidic assemblies incorporating NR (in red) fully cover the ZIF-8 particles (in grey) (Figure 3g, left). However, in this case, 3D cross-sectional images of the NR@liposome/ZIF-8 biocomposites confirmed that lipidic assemblies incorporating NR are also embedded inside the ZIF-8 particles. The penetration of lipids into the interior of the ZIF-8 particles was evidenced by the disappearance of part of the grey color in the Z-stack, which is replaced by the red color of the lipids (Figure 3g, right). We attribute the greater encapsulation of NR by the NR@liposome/ZIF-8 biocomposites to the affinity of Zn(II) to form complexes with the negatively charged phosphate group of DMPC, consistent with literature reports.^{[42][43]} Indeed, the Zn(II)-bridges between neighboring lipid molecules stabilize the gel phase of the lipid relative to the liquid-crystalline state, changing the lipid headgroup conformation, making

it less hydrophilic and provoking dehydration of the lipid bilayer. Dehydration of phospholipid headgroups due to complexation with Zn(II) cations has been suggested to increase the fusogenic potency of lipid bilayer membranes.^[43] Therefore, Zn(II) appears to be a potent divalent cation in inducing membrane fusion between liposomes and ZIF-8 particles, and by extension, in conferring ZIF-8 with greater retention of liposomes than of vesicles.

To confirm our previous observations on encapsulation, we next attempted to extract the lipids and the NR from the NR@lipid/ZIF-8 biocomposites, by treating them with dichloromethane. As seen in Figure S15, dichloromethane did not affect the morphology of the NR@vesicle/ZIF-8 or NR@liposome/ZIF-8 particles. Following extraction, the NR@vesicle/ZIF-8 biocomposites exhibited the typical white coloring of ZIF-8, suggesting that the NR/lipid assemblies had been mostly extracted (Figure 3d, right). In contrast, even after three cycles of extraction (Figure 3h, right), the NR@liposome/ZIF-8 particles remained pink, thereby suggesting that removal of the NR/lipid assemblies was more difficult due to their internal encapsulation within the ZIF-8 particles. These results were corroborated by porosity measurements: after extraction: the NR@vesicle/ZIF-8 particles ($1525 \pm 79 \text{ m}^2/\text{g}$) fully recovered the BET surface area of bare ZIF-8 particles ($1445 \pm 10 \text{ m}^2/\text{g}$), whereas the NR@liposome/ZIF-8 particles ($1355 \pm 7 \text{ m}^2/\text{g}$) only partially did so (Figure S16, Supporting Information).

Figure 3. (a,e) Schematic of the formation and structure of NR-loaded particles of the biocomposites (a) vesicle/ZIF-8 and (e) liposome/ZIF-8. (b,f) SEM images of particles of the NR-loaded biocomposites (b) NR@vesicle/ZIF-8 and (f) NR@liposome/ZIF-8. Scale bars: 1 μm (b), 2 μm (f). (c,g) Confocal microscopy images of (c) NR@vesicle/ZIF-8 and (g) NR@liposome/ZIF-8 particles. Imaris 3D reconstructions of whole NR@lipid/ZIF-8 particles stretched in Z-direction are shown on the left and Z-stack images in the middle and in the right. 3D reconstruction of the particles shows the spatial localization and penetration extend of lipid in ZIF-8 particles. Red: lipids Grey: ZIF-8. Scale bar: 500 nm. (d,h) Photos of particles of (d) NR@vesicle/ZIF-8 and (h) NR@liposome/ZIF-8, before (left) and after (right) three extractions of NR with dichloromethane.

As control experiments, we also mixed pre-synthesized ZIF-8 particles separately with the cationic NR@vesicles or NR@liposomes. The resulting mixtures contained ZIF-8 particles that

were partially and irregularly covered by lipid membranes, and isolated liposomes (Figure S17, Supporting Information). Moreover, upon exposure of each mixture to dichloromethane, the corresponding ZIF-8 particles rapidly changed from pink to white, thus demonstrating that when lipids are attached onto the particle surface, they can be easily extracted.

Finally, we explored the possibility of recovering the initial lipid assemblies through destruction of ZIF-8. To this end, we incubated the liposome/ZIF-8 biocomposites in 0.05 M aq. EDTA to destroy the ZIF-8 particles, and then dialyzed the resulting solution. Interestingly, we found that, once the ZIF-8 had been disassembled in aqueous media, the released lipids could re-self-assemble back into liposomes (Figure S18, Supporting Information).

2.2. Stability of the lipid/ZIF-8 biocomposites in physiologically relevant media

Having observed that the ZIF-8 particles within our lipid/ZIF-8 biocomposites were coated with lipids, we investigated the stability of the ZIF-8 component upon exposure of each biocomposite to physiologically relevant media that typically cause MOFs to become amorphous or to decompose and release the cargo trapped in their pores. Interestingly, for ZIF-8, degradation in such media is attributed to the affinity of polyvalent cations (Zn^{2+}) for anionic groups such as phosphates or carbonates, as their interaction leads to formation of insoluble metal phosphate or carbonates, respectively, which are readily detectable by FTIR-ATR or PXRD.^{[44][45]} Thus, we performed a comparative study of ZIF-8 (as control), vesicle/ZIF-8 and liposome/ZIF-8 particles separately incubated in water, 10X PBS (pH 7.4), SGF (pH 3) or 0.1 M bicarbonate buffer at 37 °C for 1 h, 3 h or 24 h. The concentration of particles used was based on the cytotoxicity threshold concentration of ZIF-8, and the minimum amount required to enable recuperation of the particles upon 24 h of incubation in a given medium.^[46] Following previous studies,^{[44][45]} we evaluated the stability of these particles in terms of morphology (by SEM), crystallinity (by PXRD), and chemical composition (by FTIR-ATR), both before and after incubation in each medium for each period time. Moreover, after each incubation test, we measured the pH and, using ICP-MS, the concentration of Zn(II) released (Table S7, Supporting Information).

All three particle types were stable in water (pH 6.8), experiencing only minimal effects on morphology and size (Figure S19, Supporting Information). However, the PXRD patterns for the ZIF-8 and the vesicle/ZIF-8 particles revealed a gradual reduction in crystallinity, as

evidenced by substantial decreases in the intensity of the diffraction peaks after 24 h incubation in water (**Figure 4a1 and 4a2**). Interestingly, the PXRD patterns for liposome/ZIF-8 particles suggested superior crystallinity, albeit with a partial conversion of liposome/ZIF-8 (**sod**) into the liposome/ZIF-CO₃-1 phase ($2\theta = 11^\circ$, Zn₂(mIM)₂(CO₃),^[47] referred to hereafter as *ZIF-C*) after 24 h of incubation in water. Importantly, ZIF-C is a high-density framework notably encountered in biocomposites prepared with the one-pot approach.^{[48][49]} FTIR analyses did not reveal any significant differences in stability to water among the different particle types: specifically, the vibrational modes related to the imidazole ring (1500-1350 cm⁻¹) or Zn-N bond (421 cm⁻¹) of ZIF-8 remain unchanged over time (Figure S23, Supporting Information).^[44] Consistent with the PXRD results, FTIR did confirm the presence of ZIF-C in the liposome/ZIF-8 biocomposites after incubation in water, as evidenced by additional bands at 829 cm⁻¹ and in the 1300-1400 cm⁻¹ region, corresponding to bending and asymmetric stretching modes of CO₃²⁻ (Figure S23, Supporting Information).^[48]

The results of the 24-hour incubation tests in PBS are complex and highlight the importance of using a battery of techniques for characterization. For example, SEM analysis indicated that the ZIF-8 had degraded fully, whereas the morphology of vesicle/ZIF-8 and liposome/ZIF-8 remained unchanged (Figure S20, Supporting Information). In contrast, PXRD evidenced significant amorphization of the sodalite topology for both the ZIF-8 and the vesicle/ZIF-8, revealing crystalline degradation byproducts such as crystalline zinc phosphate ($2\theta = 32^\circ$) (Figure 4b1 and 4b2)^{[50][51]}, yet did not show any significant changes in the liposome/ZIF-8. Similarly, FTIR indicated degradation of the ZIF-8 and the vesicle/ZIF-8, marked by progressive decreases in the intensity of their respective imidazole-ring vibration modes and their Zn-N bonds (421 cm⁻¹), and by the emergence of zinc salts (broad bands at 1130 cm⁻¹ to 1006 cm⁻¹, and 690 cm⁻¹ to 500 cm⁻¹)^{[44][52]}, yet did not reveal any notable change in the liposome/ZIF-8 (Figure S24, Supporting Information).

Figure 4. Comparative PXRD analysis of ZIF-8 (all 1), vesicle/ZIF-8 (all 2), and liposome/ZIF-8 (all 3) particles before (black) and after 1 h (red), 3 h (blue) or 24 h (green) incubation in (a) water, (b) 10X PBS, (c) SGF (pH 3) or (d) 0.1M bicarbonate buffer. The green star denotes the main peak of the ZIF-C phase. The blue star denotes the main peak of zinc phosphate nanoparticles.

In the SGF incubation tests, the stability of the different particle types varied by incubation time: thus, according to SEM, the ZIF-8 particles had already degraded by 1 h, the liposome/ZIF-8 particles remained stable for at least 3 h, and the vesicle/ZIF-8 remained stable after 24 h (Figure S21, Supporting Information). Importantly, PXRD revealed that ZIF-8 and

vesicle/ZIF-8 had amorphized and had transformed into zinc phosphate byproducts and ZIF-C, whereas the liposome/ZIF-8 had fully converted into liposome/ZIF-C after 24 h (Figure 4c3). With the samples incubated for 24 h, FTIR analysis revealed the gradual disappearance of the imidazole-ring vibration mode in the ZIF-8 and the vesicle/ZIF-8 (Figure S25, Supporting Information); evidenced that the liposome/ZIF-8 had fully converted into liposome/ZIF-C (829 cm^{-1}); and highlighted the presence of zinc-salt species in all three cases.

Bicarbonate proved to be the most aggressive incubation medium for all three types of particles. Indeed, SEM, PXRD and FITR analyses all indicated that ZIF-8 particles had nearly totally degraded after 1 h of incubation (Figure 4d1, S22 and S26, Supporting Information). Furthermore, SEM revealed that vesicle/ZIF-8 had remained stable for at least 3 h, and the liposome/ZIF-8 remained stable after 24 h (Figure S22, Supporting Information). However, PXRD and FITR analysis showed that both vesicle/ZIF-8 and liposome/ZIF-8 had partially transformed into the ZIF-C phase after 24 h (Figure 4d2, 4d3 and S26, Supporting Information). Notably, the degree of conversion was higher for liposome/ZIF-8 than for vesicle/ZIF-8 particles.

We also measured the pH and free-Zn content for each particle-type, in each medium and at each incubation time (Table S7, Supporting Information). In all cases the pH increased (range: 8-10), due to the degradation of ZIF-8, but the concentration of Zn^{2+} in the medium remained low.

In summary, the above data suggest that the three particle types rank as follows for stability in physiologically relevant media: liposome/ZIF-8 > vesicle/ZIF-8 > ZIF-8. We reasoned that for MOFs, the apparent gain in stability conferred by lipids, especially those from liposomes, stems from the lipids preventing surface-etching and protecting crystallinity. Note also that lipids accelerate the conversion of ZIF-8 from a sodalite topology to the denser phase ZIF-C. Indeed, according to the literature, the ZIF-C contains CO_3^{2-} and, when compared to sod ZIF-8, it exhibits distinct physical and chemical properties.^[48] Thus, the higher density of the ZIF-C phase may confer greater chemical stability and consequently, slower release of encapsulated cargo.

2.3. Encapsulation of Astaxanthin in the lipid/ZIF-8 biocomposites

Having demonstrated the encapsulation of hydrophobic molecules in our lipid/ZIF-8 biocomposites, we next turned our attention to controlling the release of their cargo. We reasoned that for drug delivery, the release-kinetics could be controlled by adjusting the lipid composition and/or self-assembly. To investigate this, we performed a series of tests using ATX, an amphiphilic ketocarotenoid found in some crustaceans, with marked hydrophobicity and with broad bio-activity profile. Indeed, ATX is a strong antioxidant; reduces oxidative stress and inflammation; strengthens the immune system; and prevents cardiovascular as well as dermatologic diseases. Accordingly, it has been used for the treatment of Alzheimer's, Parkinson's, ocular, cardiovascular, and certain inflammatory (*e.g.* rheumatoid arthritis and carpal tunnel syndrome) diseases.^[53] Furthermore, ATX is a reported chemosensitizer, not only enhancing the sensitivity of tumor cells to chemotherapy but also limiting adverse reactions.^[54] Despite its clinical utility, ATX remains limited for use in many pharmaceutical, food and cosmetic applications due its combination of poor aqueous solubility, weak dispersibility and low stability, all of which compromise its anti-oxidant capacity and its bioavailability. To overcome these barriers, researchers have been endeavoring to develop suitable delivery vehicles for ATX.^{[55][56]}

We began by synthesizing ATX@vesicle/ZIF-8 and ATX@liposome/ZIF-8 biocomposites following the same procedure previously used to encapsulate NR (Table S8, Supporting Information). Thus, in a first step, unilamellar ATX@vesicles and ATX@liposomes (**Figure 5a** and **5c**), in which ATX is encapsulated in the lipid layer, given its amphiphilicity, were prepared. Both formulations exhibited a positive charge ($> +50$ mV), and they had mean particle sizes of 677 ± 88 nm (ATX@vesicles) and 164 ± 4 nm (ATX@liposomes) (Figure S27, Supporting Information). Importantly, both were also very delicate, having sedimented out and changed color 1 week after their preparation. Next, the respective hybrid ZIF-8 biocomposites were prepared by the aforementioned protocol (Figure S28, Supporting Information). As with our previous lipid/ZIF-8 biocomposites, the resulting highly monodispersed, ATX-loaded lipid/ZIF-8 biocomposites exhibited a cubic morphology (Figure 5b and 5d), comparable crystallinity (Figure 5e), positive surface-charges, and microporosity, with measured BET surface areas of 1358 ± 8 m²/g (ATX@vesicle/ZIF-8) and 1183 ± 26 m²/g (ATX@liposome/ZIF-8), as shown in Figure S29. The mean particle sizes were 172 ± 3 nm (ATX@vesicle/ZIF-8) and 185 ± 1 nm (ATX@liposome/ZIF-8) (Figure S30). Both

biocomposites had ATX encapsulation efficiencies (EE) of > 99%, with values of 14 mg ATX/g ATX@liposome/ZIF-8 and 11 mg ATX / g ATX@vesicle/ZIF-8.^[39] We further confirmed encapsulation of ATX by FTIR, in which the characteristic peak at 1551 cm^{-1} from the C=C in the hexatomic ring of ATX was present in the spectra of both ATX@vesicle/ZIF-8 and ATX@liposome/ZIF-8 (Figure S31, Supporting Information).

Figure 5. (a,c) Cryo-TEM images of ATX-loaded (a) CTAB/Chol vesicles and (c) DMPC-Chol-Chol(+) liposomes. Scale bar: 200 nm. (b,d) SEM images of particles of (f) ATX@vesicle/ZIF-8 and (g) ATX@liposome/ZIF-8. Scale bar: 500 nm. (e) PXRD spectra for ATX@vesicle/ZIF-8 (blue) and ATX@liposome/ZIF-8 (green), as compared to ZIF-8 (black).

To ascertain the contribution of the lipids to the encapsulation of ATX onto/into the lipid/ZIF-8 biocomposites, we attempted to encapsulate ATX directly into ZIF-8, without using any lipids, following two ways: *in situ*, during synthesis of ZIF-8; and using pre-synthesized ZIF-8. In both cases, the EE was negligible (0%, *in situ*) and very low (8%, pre-synthesized). Next, we attempted to integrate ATX with ZIF-8 using cholesterol as an intermediate to facilitate interaction between ZIF-8 and the highly hydrophobic ATX. However, even in this case, the EE was extremely low (3%). Together, these results corroborated that in ATX@lipid/ZIF-8 biocomposites, the lipid components are responsible for the encapsulation of ATX.

Next, we performed an *in vitro* evaluation of the cytotoxicity of ATX@lipid/ZIF-8, lipid/ZIF-8, and ZIF-8 particles using NIH-3T3 mouse cells at particle concentrations ranging from 25 to 200 μM for 24 hours.^{[57][58]} As illustrated in **Figure 6a**, none of the particles exhibited toxicity at the indicated concentrations except for the highest dose (200 μM) after 24 hours of incubation. Vesicle/ZIF-8 biocomposites notably displayed higher toxicity on NIH-3T3 cells (EC_{50} = 109.6 μM) compared to the liposome/ZIF-8 biocomposite (EC_{50} = 160.2 μM). However, when ATX is loaded in both hybrid biocomposites, the toxicity of both types of biocomposites becomes similar, with EC_{50} = 158.7 μM for ATX@liposome/ZIF-8 and EC_{50} = 157.7 μM for ATX@vesicle/ZIF-8.

We then sought to evaluate the antioxidant capacity of the ATX encapsulated within each type of lipid/ZIF-8 biocomposite and compare the values to that of ATX alone. To this end, we performed a redox test using a model substrate for ATX: 2,2-diphenyl-1-picrylhydrazyl (DPPH \cdot) radical, a stable free radical that reacts with the hydrogen provided by antioxidants (radical scavengers) such as ATX to form the stable product DPPH-H. This reaction can be monitored by a color change (absorbance was measured at 523 nm): the initial DPPH \cdot radical is purple, whereas the product, DPPH-H, is yellow.^[59] With this test, the antioxidant capacity (*i.e.* radical inhibition) of ATX can be measured, and then expressed as a percentage. The results, from highest to lowest antioxidant capacity (reported in parentheses), were: ATX@liposome/ZIF-8 particles (40%) > ATX@vesicle/ZIF-8 biocomposite = free ATX (both: 30%). The antioxidant capacities of the three types of particles were statistically compared, revealing no significant differences among the samples ($P > 0.05$). Together, these results demonstrate that the antioxidant capacity of ATX is preserved after encapsulation within the biocomposites.^{[60][61]}

In addition, the antioxidant properties of ATX-loaded in lipid/ZIF-8 biocomposites were tested *in vitro* using the mouse fibroblast cell line (NIH-3T3) against induced oxidative stress, following a previously standardized protocol that uses hydrogen peroxide as the inducer.^{[57][58]} The results showed a statistically significant reduction in cell viability ($p < 0.05$) in control cells exposed to hydrogen peroxide compared to those cells incubated with the ATX@lipid/ZIF-8 biocomposites (Figure 6b). This fact highlights the antioxidant effect of the ATX-loaded in the lipid/ZIF-8 biocomposites at the cellular level. Furthermore, it has been observed that this cell protective effect can be enhanced by increasing the concentration of biocomposite up to a level (150 μM) where the particles are not cytotoxic.

Having demonstrated the encapsulation, antioxidant capacity and stability of ATX within our lipid/ZIF-8 biocomposites, we next explored the *in vitro* digestion of ATX@vesicle/ZIF-8 and ATX@liposome/ZIF-8 biocomposites similarly to our previous tests with the NR-loaded analogs, again using the method INFOGEST 2.0.^[62] We began with the tests in SGF (pH 3; 37 °C): after 2 h incubation, each biocomposite released only a small amount (< 10%) of ATX (Figure 6c and 6d). Next, we submitted the digested sample from above to SIF (pH 7.4; 37 °C). After 3 h incubation, the ATX@liposome/ZIF-8 had released an additional 19% of their original encapsulated ATX in a sustained fashion. In contrast, after 2 h of incubation in SIF, the release of ATX from the ATX@vesicle/ZIF-8, which had occurred in a large burst of 54%, plateaued. Thus, over the 5 h combined incubation (SGF + SIF), the total cumulative ATX-release for each biocomposite was 29% (ATX@liposome/ZIF-8) and 64% (ATX@vesicle/ZIF-8). Interestingly, these results are consistent with reported values for ATX@PEG-polycaprolactone micelles, for which the ATX-encapsulation efficiency was 97% releasing 65% of their original encapsulated ATX after 5 h incubation in PBS medium (pH 7.4).^[60]

Having measured the release of ATX after the 5 h combined incubation (SGF + SIF), we then characterized the resultant ATX@vesicle/ZIF-8 and ATX@liposome/ZIF-8 particles by SEM and PXRD. SEM indicated that neither biocomposite had undergone any major surface degradation (Figure S33, Supporting Information). Although PXRD corroborated this finding for the vesicle/ZIF-8 (Figure 6e), it did reveal that the liposome/ZIF-8 had transformed into the denser liposome/ZIF-C phase (Figure 6f). Thus, we attributed the slower and lower release of ATX from the liposome/ZIF-8 relative to that from the vesicle/ZIF-8 to two factors: firstly, to the ZIF-C transformation of the former, as this would hinder release of ATX in both SGF and SIF; and secondly, to the fact that within the ZIF-8 scaffold, the lipid assemblies in liposome/ZIF-8 are more internalized than the lipid assemblies in vesicle/ZIF-8 (Figure 3).

Overall, these results demonstrate that: 1) lipid/ZIF-8 biocomposites can be used to encapsulate ATX and to gradually release it in physiological media; and 2) the release kinetics can be modulated by the choice of lipid assembly used.

Figure 6. (a) *In vitro* cytotoxicity of ZIF-8, vesicle/ZIF-8, liposome/ZIF-8, ATX@vesicle/ZIF-8 and ATX@liposome/ZIF-8 biocomposites to mouse NIH-3T3 cells. Cell viability of NIH-3T3 cells after 24 h incubation with different biocomposites at various concentrations (25 μM to 200 μM). Untreated cells were used as control (marked as C). Data represents the mean \pm standard error of the mean of three independent experiments. (b) Antioxidant effect of ATX@lipid/ZIF-8 biocomposites on the viability of

NIH-3T3 cells exposed to oxidative stress with hydrogen peroxide (1 mM for 2 h) compared to control cells (* $p < 0.05$). (c,d) Profile of ATX-release from (c) ATX@vesicle/ZIF-8 and (d) ATX@liposome/ZIF-8 in SGF (pH 3) or SIF (pH 7.4) media at 37 °C (mean \pm standard deviation, $n=3$). (e,f) PXRD spectra of particles of (e) ATX@vesicle/ZIF-8 and (f) ATX@liposome/ZIF-8 before incubation (black), after 2 h incubation in SGF (blue), and after 5 h combined incubation (2 h SGF + 3 h SIF; red). The green star denotes the main peak of the ZIF-C phase. The blue star denotes the main peak of zinc phosphate nanoparticles.

Mucoadhesion refers to the retention of a substance in mucus or on mucus membranes in the body.^[63] The efficacy of oral drug-delivery systems demands strong mucoadhesion in the gastrointestinal (GI) tract, as this enables the delivery particles to fully engage with intestinal epithelial cells and subsequently be transported into the bloodstream. Mucoadhesion can be evaluated by measuring the amount of the glycoprotein mucin, a major component of mucus that envelops surfaces in the digestive tract, absorbed by a given test-substance. Thus, seeking to further explore the potential of our lipid/ZIF-8 biocomposites as drug-delivery vehicles, we performed such a test by incubating mucin (0.5 mg/mL) separately with particles of each biocomposite (2 mg/mL), or of ZIF-8, in water at 37 °C for 16 h. The mucoadhesion values, expressed as a percentage of mucin that had adhered to the test substance, were (highest to lowest): ATX@liposome/ZIF-8 particles (29%) > ATX@vesicle/ZIF-8 (18%) > ZIF-8 (15%). The mucoadhesion of the three types of particles were compared statistically. It was observed that the mucoadhesion of ATX@liposome/ZIF-8 particles were significantly greater than that of ATX@vesicle/ZIF-8 particles ($P < 0.05$) and ZIF-8 particles ($P < 0.05$). No significant difference was observed between the mucoadhesiveness of ATX@vesicle/ZIF-8 and ZIF-8 particles ($P > 0.05$). We attributed the apparently greater attraction of mucin to ATX@liposome/ZIF-8 to the interactions between the mucin molecules and the phosphatidyl groups on the ATX@liposome/ZIF-8 particles. Collectively, these results together confirm that our bio-composites have enhanced mucin adhesion properties when compared with pristine ZIF-8.

3. Conclusion

We have prepared two lipid/ZIF-8 biocomposites by combining the ZIF-8 building blocks with either of two self-assembled lipids: CTAB-Chol vesicles or DMPC-Chol-Chol+ liposomes (lipid bilayer). The integration of these lipidic assemblies onto/into ZIF-8 particles occurs

through ongoing supramolecular disassembly/reassembly processes, while influencing the creation of ZIF-8 particles. In the resultant vesicle/ZIF-8 biocomposite, the vesicles coat the surface of the ZIF-8, whereas in the resultant liposome/ZIF-8 biocomposite, the liposomes both adhere to the surface and penetrate the interior of the ZIF-8. In various physiologically relevant media, the liposome/ZIF-8 particles degrade much more slowly than do the vesicle/ZIF-8 ones, which in turn degrade more slowly than bare ZIF-8 particles. Thus, we concluded that in the biocomposites, the lipid - especially those self-assembled in liposomes - contribute to the stability of the ZIF-8 by preventing surface etching and maintaining their crystalline structure in challenging environments. Besides conferring this shielding effect, in certain media the lipids also accelerate the conversion of ZIF-8 from a sodalite topology to the denser ZIF-C phase.

We also confirmed that our lipid/ZIF-8 biocomposites could be used to encapsulate hydrophobic cargo, which we demonstrated for the fluorophore NR and the antioxidant drug ATX, by pre-encapsulating them within the membranes of the vesicles and liposomes. Both biocomposites exhibited very high encapsulation efficiencies for ATX, which, once released, retained its therapeutic antioxidant capacity. Interestingly, *in-vitro* digestion of ATX-loaded lipid/ZIF-8 biocomposites revealed distinct ATX-release kinetics in SIF (pH 7.4). The liposome/ZIF-8 particles released ATX in a sustained way, whereas the vesicle/ZIF-8 particles did so in a burst. We attributed this difference to the aforementioned crystalline phase-transition of liposome/ZIF-8 into liposome/ZIF-C, together with the fact that ATX is more internalized in liposome/ZIF-8 than in vesicle/ZIF-8. Our findings also highlight that with MOF particles used for drug-delivery, potential phase transformations provoked by contact with biological media should be considered. Lastly, and very important, the preliminary results on the mucoadhesion of our biocomposites suggest that, once administered orally, they might exhibit prolonged residence in the mucosa of the intestinal tract, which would ultimately enable effective physiologic delivery of ATX.^[64]

Together, our findings from this study underscore the versatility and benefits of our hybrid lipid/ZIF-8 biocomposites for encapsulating hydrophobic and inherently unstable drugs. Our preliminary biocomposites should inform the design of future lipid/MOF systems as drug delivery vehicles. Namely, we believe that the controlled release property of these systems could be personalized through strategic combinations of the lipid assemblies, MOF and cargo, thereby offering an alternative, tailored and effective delivery modality.

4. Experimental Section

Chemicals: Cholesterol (Chol, 92.5%), hexadecyltrimethylammonium bromide (CTAB, 98%), 1,2-dimyristoyl-sn-glycero-3-phosphocholine (DMPC), cholesteryl 3 β -N-(dimethylaminoethyl)-carbamate hydrochloride (Chol+, 99%), Nile red (NR), astaxanthin (ATX, 97%), zinc acetate dihydrate ($\text{Zn}(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$, 98%), 2-methylimidazole (2-MiM, 99%), pepsin from porcine gastric mucosa, pancreatine (4 x USP), bile extract porcine, gastric lipase, calcium chloride dihydrate ($\text{MgCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$, 98%), ammonium carbonate $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{CO}_3$, 99.9%), potassium chloride (KCl, 99%), sodium bicarbonate (NaHCO_3 , $\geq 97\%$), sodium chloride (NaCl, 99%), monopotassium phosphate (KH_2PO_4 , $\geq 99.0\%$), sodium hydroxide (NaOH, 98%), sodium carbonate (Na_2CO_3 , 99.5%), magnesium chloride hexahydrate ($\text{MgCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$, 99%), 2,2-difenil-1-picirilhidrazil (DPPH), and PBS tablets were obtained from Merck KGaA (Darmstadt, Germany). All water used was purified by the Milli-Q technique.

Synthesis of CTAB-Chol vesicles: In a typical synthesis, 1 mL of 2.5 mM Chol in acetone/dichloromethane (1:1) was mixed with 3 mL of 2.5 mM CTAB in water. For the preparation of vesicles loaded with hydrophobic actives, 1.2 mg/mL of NR or 2 mg/mL of ATX were added to the Chol organic phase. The mixture was then sonicated with an ultrasonic probe (Vibracell Sonifier, Sonic and Materials Inc., Newtown, USA; 20 kHz; 50% amplitude) for 2 min, until the liposomes were homogeneously dispersed. The mixture was stirred at 40 °C for 5 h and then, at 25 °C overnight for evaporation of organic solvents and formation of vesicles.

Synthesis of DMPC-Chol-Chol+ liposomes: The liposomes were prepared using the thin-film hydration method.^[65] Firstly, a chloroform solution (100 mg/mL) containing 107 μL of DMPC, 18 μL of Chol and 60 μL of cholesteryl Chol+ (molar ratio = 1.0:0.3:0.7) was prepared. The total lipid concentration was 16 mM. For the preparation of liposomes that contained a hydrophobic active as cargo, either NR (1.2 mg/mL) or ATX (2 mg/mL) were pre-added to the lipid chloroform phase. The organic solvent was removed under vacuum and nitrogen to afford a dry lipid film, which was then hydrated with 2 mL of water under stirring for 1 h. Under these conditions the stacks of liquid crystalline lipid bilayers became fluid and swelled, resulting in their detachment during agitation and their self-closure to form large multilamellar vesicles (LMVs). Unilamellar liposomes were obtained by homogenizing the LMV suspension using an ultrasonic probe (20 kHz; 50% amplitude) for 2 min, until the liposomes were homogeneously dispersed.

Synthesis of ZIF-8 particles: In a typical synthesis, a solution of $\text{Zn}(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (0.273 M) in 5 mL of water was added dropwise into 5 mL of an aqueous solution of 2-MiM (2.72 M) and CTAB (0.54 mM) with gentle stirring for a few seconds.^[29] The resulting particles were isolated, and then cleaned with deionized (DI) water by centrifugation (9000 rpm; 10 min). Finally, the resultant particles were frozen at $-85\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 2 h, and then lyophilized for 2 days.

Synthesis of hybrid lipid/ZIF-8 biocomposites: A 1-mL aliquot of vesicles or liposomes (empty, or pre-loaded with NR or ATX) was mixed with a solution of 0.273 M $\text{Zn}(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ dissolved in water (5 mL). The resultant solution was added dropwise to 5 mL of an aqueous solution of 2-MiM (2.72 M) and CTAB (0.54 mM) with gentle stirring for a few seconds. The resulting transparent mixture turned turbid after 15 s and was left undisturbed at room temperature for 2 h. The resulting particles were isolated, and then cleaned with deionized (DI) water by centrifugation (9000 rpm; 10 min). Finally, the particles were frozen at $-85\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 2 h, and then lyophilized for 2 days.

Characterization: Particle-size distribution was measured by dynamic light scattering (DLS) combined with noninvasive backscatter technology (Malvern Zetasizer; Malvern Instruments, United Kingdom). The stability of the particles was evaluated by measuring their zeta potential with an electrophoretic mobility and light-scattering analyzer (Malvern Zetasizer). Morphology was studied by cryogenic transmission electron microscopy (cryo-TEM), on a JEM 1400 microscope (JEOL, Japan), and by Field-Emission Scanning Electron Microscopy (FE-SEM), on Quanta 650 and Magellan 400L microscopes (FEI, USA), each equipped with an energy-selective backscattered detector (EBS) and a coupled energy-dispersive X-ray spectrometer (EDS Oxford INCA) operating at low voltage. Crystallinity and phase-purity were determined by powder X-ray diffraction (PXRD) measurements taken on an X'Pert PRO MPD diffractometer (Panalytical). Surface area was determined by BET measurements performed with an ASAP-2000 instrument from Micromeritics. Chemical composition was analyzed by FTIR-ATR spectroscopy, using a Tensor 27 FT-IR spectrometer equipped with an MVP-Pro ATR module (Bruker, USA).

Encapsulation efficiency: The encapsulation efficiencies (EE) for NR and ATX as cargo were calculated according to the equation $\text{EE} (\%) = [(C_{A,\text{total}} - C_{A,\text{out}})/C_{A,\text{total}}] \times 100\%$, where $C_{A,\text{total}}$ is the initial NR or ATX concentration, and $C_{A,\text{out}}$ is the concentration of free (non-

encapsulated) NR or ATX. To measure the $C_{A,out}$, freshly prepared particles were centrifuged at 6000 rpm for 10 min at 5 °C in a 100 kDa MWCO Amicon Ultra-4 Centrifugal filters (Millipore). Next, NR and ATX were each extracted from supernatant aliquots using chloroform (for NR) or dichloromethane (for ATX), and then quantified by UV-Vis spectroscopy, using a Nanodrop ND-1000 (Thermo Scientific, USA). The NR was linearly detected in a range from 0.7 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ to 22 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ (Abs at 537 nm, $r^2=0.999$) in chloroform, whereas the ATX was linearly detected in a range from 0.1 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ to 10 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ (Abs at 478 nm, $r^2=0.999$) in dichloromethane. All experiments were done in triplicate.

Interaction of ZIF-8 with lipids from vesicles or liposomes: To study the vesicle/ZIF-8 and lipid/ZIF-8 particle formation, time-resolved SAXS plots were collected at the Austrian SAXS beamline of the ELETTRA synchrotron light source.^[66] The experiments were operated at a photon energy of 8 keV covering the range of momentum transfer q , $q = 4\pi \sin(\theta/2)/\lambda$ (θ scattering angle, λ X-ray wavelength), between 0.3 and 8.0 nm^{-1} using a pixel detector (Pilatus3 1M, Dectris Ltd, Baden, Switzerland) at a sample-to-detector distance of 820.7 mm. The q -scale was determined with silver behenate as a calibration sample. We monitored the kinetic of the ZIF nucleation and growth using an SFM-4 stopped-flow apparatus (Bio-Logic, Grenoble, France) designed for synchrotron Radiation SAXS investigations.^[67] Two independently controlled syringes were filled with the biocomposite precursors (see SI). The precursors were mixed within the stopped-flow apparatus and transferred to a quartz capillary along the X-ray beam path. The mixing time of the applied turbulent mixer was < 20 ms. The start of the mixing sequence was triggered by the X-ray data-acquisition system. Images were acquired with an initial time resolution of 100 ms (detector: Pilatus3 1M, Dectris Ltd, Baden, Switzerland) over a time course of *ca.* 20 min with reduced time resolution and larger wait periods between the images to reduce the X-ray radiation damage. The scattering plots were corrected for fluctuations of the primary X-ray beam intensity and variations of the transmission. The scattering plot of a capillary filled with Milli-Q water was collected and subtracted as background from the data with the appropriate normalization.

To confirm the location of lipid assemblies (vesicles or liposomes) within the vesicle/ZIF-8 and liposome/ZIF-8 biocomposites, fluorescently labeled, NR-loaded samples (30 μL) were placed on a coated glass slide and observed by confocal laser microscopy, using a Zeiss LSM 980 microscope with an Airyscan 2 detector (Carl Zeiss Microscopy GmbH, Germany). NR@lipid/ZIF-8 particles were observed using reflection and fluorescence modes. Confocal data of NR@lipid/ZIF-8 particles were processed with Imaris software to create 3D

reconstructions. This allowed for the analysis of the spatial localization and extent of lipid penetration within the ZIF-8 particles. For these experiments, NR@lipid/ZIF-8 particles were prepared and cleaned as described above. However, in this case, the ZIF-8 reaction time was increased to 24 h to increase the size of the synthesized particles, as particles made under the standard synthetic conditions would have been below the resolution limit of the optical microscope.

Stability in physiological media: Vesicle/ZIF-8, liposome/ZIF-8 and — for comparison — bare ZIF-8 particles were independently incubated in the following physiologically-relevant media: water, phosphate buffered saline (10X PBS, pH 7.4), simulated gastric fluid (SGF; pH 3) or 0.1 M bicarbonate (pH 9.68). Briefly, 50 mg of each type of particle were separately added to 30 mL of each medium independently at 37 °C under magnetic stirring. Independent samples were allowed to stir for 1 h, 3 h or 24 h. The PBS was prepared by dissolving one tablet in 200 mL of ultrapure water (0.01 M phosphate buffer, 0.0027 M potassium chloride and 0.137 M sodium chloride). The SGF, an aqueous solution of KCl, KH₂PO₄, NaHCO₃, NaCl, MgCl₂, (NH₄)₂CO₃ and CaCl₂, was prepared according to the INFOGEST method.^[62] The 0.1 M bicarbonate solution was prepared by adding 1.25 g sodium bicarbonate and 0.55 g sodium carbonate to 250 mL Milli-Q water, and then adjusting the pH to 9.68 using 1 M sodium hydroxide. After incubation, the samples were filtered through a Kitasato filter with a 0.1 μm nylon membrane. The resultant filtrates and solids were separately analyzed to measure the particle-degradation in each medium. Both the pH, and the concentration of free Zn, of the filtrates were measured, the latter by inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry (ICP-MS) in a Model 790 mass spectrometer (Agilent, USA). The morphology of the particles was analyzed by SEM; their crystallinity by PXRD; and their chemical structure by FTIR-ATR. Each sample was analyzed in triplicate.

Antioxidant capacity of ATX: The antioxidant capacity (AC) of encapsulated ATX was determined using the 2,2-diphenyl-1-picrylhydrazyl free radical (DPPH) method.^[68] Briefly, 20 mg of ATX-loaded, hybrid lipid/ZIF-8 particles were dispersed in 1 mL of distilled water. Next, 2 mL of a solution of DPPH (0.125 mM) in MeOH were added. The mixture was left stirring at 400 rpm for 3 h. Subsequently, the sample was filtered through a 0.25 μm membrane filter, and the resultant supernatant was analyzed by UV-Vis spectroscopy at 523 nm. As standard control, a mixture of 1 mL of water and 2 mL of a solution of DPPH (0.125 mM) in MeOH was used. The antioxidant capacity was quantified using the following equation: $AC (\%) = [(A_C -$

$A_{\text{sample}}/A_{\text{C}}] \times 100$, where A_{C} is the absorbance of the control standard, and A_{sample} is the absorbance of the ATX-loaded particles.

In vitro cytotoxicity and antioxidant activity of ATX@lipid/ZIF-8 biocomposites: Mouse fibroblasts (NIH 3T3) were cultured in Dulbecco's modified Eagle's medium (Gibco DMEM + GlutaMAX, high glucose, pyruvate) supplemented with 10% fetal bovine serum (FBS). To test *in vitro* cytotoxicity of the biocomposites, NIH-3T3 cells were incubated with ATX@lipid/ZIF-8 particles, and then the effect of biocomposites on cell viability was assessed using the XTT (2,3-bis-(2-methoxy-4-nitro-5-sulphophenyl)-2 H-tetrazolium-5-carboxanilide) assay (Invitrogen CyQUANT XTT) after 24 h incubation time. Cells were seeded into 96-well plates at a concentration of 1×10^4 cells/well and incubated for 24 h. The medium was then replaced with fresh medium containing a suspension of the biocomposites at concentrations ranging from 25 to 200 μM . After another 24 h incubation, aliquots of XTT solution were added to each well, and the resulting color was quantified at 450 nm using a spectrophotometric plate reader (SpectraMax iD3). Cell viability was expressed as a percentage relative to the untreated control level. All measurements were performed in triplicate across three independent experiments. As controls, cells were either exposed to 5% - 10% DMSO or left untreated. The same procedure was used to evaluate the cytotoxicity of ZIF-8 and empty lipid/ZIF-8 particles on NIH 3T3 cells. Dose-response curves were fitted using a sigmoidal dose response curve model provided in the GraphPad Prism 5.0 (GraphPad software, USA). EC50 value was derived from these fitted curves for single experiments.

To assess the antioxidant activity of the biocomposites, NIH 3T3 cells were seeded as previously described. After a 24-h incubation, the medium was replaced with fresh medium containing the biocomposites at concentrations of 100 μM and 150 μM . The cells were then incubated for an additional 24 h. After incubation, all cells, except the control group, were exposed to 1 mM hydrogen peroxide for 2 h. Subsequently, the cells were briefly washed with PBS, and cell viability was determined using the XTT method, as previously described.

Static in-vitro simulation of gastrointestinal digestion of ATX@lipid/ZIF-8: In-vitro digestion of ATX@lipid/ZIF-8 was performed using the recently updated INFOGEST 2.0 method.^[62] Briefly, the particles were sequentially exposed to simulated salivary, gastric, and intestinal phases with the appropriate gastrointestinal tract components, pH values, incubation times and temperature (37 °C). Thus, to first simulate salivary exposure, 30 mg of particles and 1 mL simulated salivary fluid (SSF) were stirred for 2 min at pH 7. Next, to simulate subsequent

gastric digestion, 2 mL of SGF, containing pepsin (2000 U/mL) and gastric lipase (60 U/mL), were added to the mixture resulting from the oral exposure, and stirred at pH 3 for different incubation periods: 0.25 h, 0.50 h, 0.75 h, 1 h, 1.5 h and 2 h. Finally, to mimic intestinal digestion, 4 mL of simulated intestinal fluid (SIF), containing bile salts (10 mM) and pancreatin (100 U/mL), were added to mixture resulting from the gastric digestion and stirred at pH 7 for different incubation periods: 0.25 h, 0.50 h, 0.75 h, 1 h, 1.5 h, 2 h, 3 h, 4 h and 5 h. The full compositions of SSF, SGF, and SIF are summarized in the method INFOGEST 2.0.^[62] At each incubation time point, the respective reactions were quenched, by either adjusting the pH of the gastric samples to 7 with NaOH (1M), or subjecting the intestinal samples to heat-shock treatment (100 °C for 5 min). The resultant mixtures were filtered through a 0.22 µm syringe filter, and the ATX was extracted from the filtrate with dichloromethane under stirring for 1 h, and then quantified by UV-Vis spectroscopy at 478 nm.

In-vitro bio-adsorption and mucoadhesion studies: Mucoadhesion, a parameter that reflects the extent to which a given material is attracted to mucus or a mucus membrane, was calculated as the amount of mucin adsorbed by particles in a certain time period.^[69] Briefly, biocomposites (4 mg/mL) were mixed and incubated with type III mucin (0.5 mg/mL) from porcine stomach, at 37 °C for 16 h. Then, the suspension was centrifuged (10,000 rpm; 4 °C; 15 min), and the concentration of free mucin in the supernatant was determined by the Periodic Acid Schiff (PAS) colorimetric method.^[70] Standard samples of mucin were measured using the same procedure, enabling generation of a calibration curve.

Statistical analysis: All results were analyzed using R software. For normally distributed samples, one-way ANOVA and Post Hoc Tukey test were used. The polydispersity index (PdI), defined as the square of the ratio of the standard deviation/mean diameter, was determined as a measure of the width of the particle size distribution.

Supporting Information

Supporting Information is available from the Wiley Online Library or from the author.

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M.C.-S, F.A., L.M. J.F. and M.G.-B. synthesized and characterized the ZIF-8 particles and lipid/ZIF-8 biocomposites and performed the encapsulation, stability and release experiments.

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Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no competing financial interest.

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Lipid/ZIF-8 biocomposites based on liposomes or vesicles: *in-situ* formation, and preliminary evaluation as delivery vehicles for hydrophobic drugs

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Integrating lipid self-assemblies with metal-organic frameworks (MOFs) creates biocomposites ideal for encapsulation, protection, and delivery of functional species. This study reports the *in-situ* formation of ZIF-8 MOF particles with lipid self-assemblies, generating hybrid lipid/ZIF-8 biocomposites. These biocomposites encapsulate hydrophobic molecules like Astaxanthin drug, showing distinct release kinetics and potential crystalline phase transitions in various media, valuable for drug delivery applications.

